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POSSIBILITIES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION MEANS IN THE FORMATION OF VOLITIONAL QUALITIES IN SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract: The article explores the essence and structure of the physical education tools utilized in the author's dissertation research, their potential, their expression during adolescence, and the specific features of their development. It analyzes the use of a comprehensive program in developing volitional qualities, the significance of exercises in nurturing such qualities, and the methods applied to foster traits like overcoming various challenges encountered by schoolchildren in the learning process.

Key words: volitional qualities, physical education potential, development of volitional qualities, physical education tools.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada muallifning dissertatsion tadqiqotida qo'llanilgan jismoniy tarbiya vositalarining mazmuni va tuzilishi, ularning imkoniyatlari, o'smirlik davrida namoyon bo'lishi hamda shakllanish xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Irodaviy sifatlarni shakllantirishda kompleks dasturdan foydalanish usullari, mashqlarning irodaviy sifatlarni rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati, shuningdek, o'quvchilarda o'quv jarayonidagi turli qiyinchiliklarni yengish qobiliyatini shakllantirishga qaratilgan metodlar o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: irodaviy sifatlarni, jismoniy tarbiyaning imkoniyatlari, irodaviy sifatlarni shakllantirish, jismoniy tarbiya vositalari.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются сущность и структура средств физического воспитания, использованных в диссертационном исследовании автора, их потенциал, проявление в подростковом возрасте и особенности формирования. Анализируются методы использования комплексной программы в формировании волевых качеств, значение упражнений в развитии таких качеств, а также методы формирования у школьников способности преодолевать различные трудности в учебном процессе.

Ключевые слова: волевые качества, потенциал физического воспитания, формирование волевых качеств, средства физического воспитания.

INTRODUCTION

Throughout the history of the development of philosophical, psychological, and pedagogical knowledge, from ancient times to the present day, the problem of the concept of "will" has always attracted the attention of scientists. None of the scientific disciplines has denied the existence of this phenomenon in humans. Regardless of who wrote them and when, almost all textbooks in psychology and pedagogy have addressed this issue in one way or another. Let us now turn to the basic philosophical, psychological, and pedagogical definitions of the concept of will and its manifestations. In the history of European philosophy, it has had two main meanings. According to classical rationalist traditions, will is the ability of the mind to self-determine, including the creation of moral and specific causality. F. W. Schelling, Schopenhauer, E. Hartmann, F. Nietzsche, and partly A. Bergson, in the voluntaristic tradition, viewed will as a fundamental property of pre-cognitive being and as the basis of all explanatory models.

In psychology, the concept of "will" is presented as a complex mental process that makes a person active and motivates them to act in accordance with a purpose and achieve set goals. Unlike other psychological phenomena, will is not measured by specific metrics and evaluations, but this does not rule out the possibility of studying the human will scientifically, especially experimentally ^[1].

Let's consider the following definitions, as they are of particular interest in the context of our research:

1. Will is a certain internal psychological force capable of controlling other psychological phenomena and human behavior.

2. Will is a form of internal control over a person's actions and is associated with their consciousness, thinking, and decision-making.
3. Willpower represents the highest level of regulation of human behavior. Volitional behavior is called such because a person can control it.
4. Willpower is the ability of a person to set and achieve difficult goals and to overcome serious internal and external obstacles.
5. Willpower is when a person consciously chooses one of several equally available behavioral options and commits to it.
6. Willpower is a trait that distinguishes human behavior from animal behavior. Animals have no will; they act under the influence of external environmental factors or internal organic impulses.
7. Will is the source of human conscious and perceptual actions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

As observed, in understanding the concept of “will,” it is impossible to separate purely psychological or pedagogical aspects, as it influences all areas of human activity. Scholars such as E.P. Ilin, L.S. Vygotsky, and I.D. Bex analyzed various aspects of the formation and development of different categories of willpower among students, military cadets, and sports school trainees. These studies allow us to draw the following conclusions: there is a clear pedagogical interpretation of will and willpower; in pedagogy, the problem of will and volitional qualities is examined not in terms of their essence, but in terms of their formation and development, thus the subject of research focuses not on the nature of phenomena but on their forms and methods of development; the foundation for designing various systems, models, programs, and technologies is based on the authors' chosen psychological concept of will and volitional qualities, aligned with the goals and objectives of the study.

Our understanding of the nature and content of volitional qualities in students is based on the following theoretical principles: volitional qualities are relatively independent and stable mental formations, the content of which is determined by the stage of ontogeny, personal experience, knowledge, skills, formed motives, and beliefs; volitional qualities operate as a unified, open, dynamic, and integrated system, in which components are interdependent and vary depending on the objective conditions of a particular activity, ensuring the dominance of specific volitional traits; the system-forming function of volitional qualities is the generalized capacity to overcome various obstacles encountered on the path to achieving a goal; the success of an activity and the development of volitional qualities are interrelated: volitional qualities are shaped by the nature and content of activity, while, in turn, the success of an activity is influenced by the level of development of these qualities [2, 3, 4]. In pedagogy, the term tools carry ambiguous meanings and is employed by researchers in various contexts.

These include teaching aids, educational resources, developmental tools, elements of humanitarian culture, and more. Tools are essential and integral components of the educational process and are often seen as a means to enhance the effectiveness of any instructional or upbringing process through specific forms and methods. Therefore, the most widely accepted definition of tools in pedagogy is the following: pedagogical tools are material (man-made) and natural objects used in the learning process as carriers of information and as instruments for organizing and managing students' educational activities [5]. Based on this general definition, any object used within the educational process may be regarded as a “tool.” There is, however, some variation among researchers regarding the typology of tools. Most commonly in pedagogy, the following categories of teaching aids are distinguished: printed, electronic, audiovisual, visual, demonstrative, presentational, educational devices, simulators and sports equipment, and teaching materials—each further classified into specific subtypes.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article focuses on the provision of sports equipment and gym facilities, sports grounds, and school stadiums as key tools for education. In this context, they can be regarded as instruments for solving specific tasks related to physical education, training, and upbringing. Indeed, gymnastic ladders, beams, balls, and similar tools do not independently develop any volitional qualities; rather, they serve as “material tools” used in physical education to address certain pedagogical goals. Therefore, in order to determine the structure and potential of physical education tools used to cultivate students' volitional qualities, the author finds it necessary to refer to the theory and methodology of physical education as an independent pedagogical discipline. The theory and methodology of physical education emphasize that its tools include exercises, the healing forces of nature, and hygiene rules and norms [6]. Let us now examine each group of physical education tools based on these principles:

Exercise. Most researchers consider exercise to be a fundamental tool of physical education. Exercise refers to a set of movements formed and organized in accordance with specific principles, aimed at fulfilling

the objectives of physical education. In this context, the term “physical” reflects the essence of the activity as manifested through the movements of the human body and its parts in space and time. The term “exercise” also implies a purposeful repetition of actions designed to influence a person’s physical and mental characteristics and improve performance of those actions. That is, exercise is regarded both as a distinct motor activity and as a repeated process.

The effectiveness of exercise depends primarily on its content. According to sports physiologists, the content of an exercise is the sum of physiological, psychological, and biomechanical processes that occur in the body during the activity. This content defines its health-promoting value, its educational impact, and its influence on the development of personality traits—particularly volitional qualities—that are of special interest in this study.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The impact of exercise on personality development lies in the fact that individuals overcome challenges and regulate emotions during physical activity. This process nurtures vital characteristics, including volitional qualities. Most physical activity in schools is carried out in groups of peers. In many situations, the actions of one student influence those of others, which becomes especially evident during sports competitions and outdoor games. The ability to maintain self-control, to conform to the collective will, to make optimal decisions, and to assist peers regardless of personal ambitions are all volitional qualities actively fostered through exercise. The healing powers of nature also play a significant role for those engaged in physical activities. Changes in weather conditions can enhance physical activity, pose additional challenges in performing exercises, and thereby increase the effectiveness of volitional development. In the process of students’ physical education, the healing forces of nature are typically utilized in two ways: as factors that create the most favorable conditions for exercise. In this case, the positive influence of exercise on schoolchildren is amplified.

In forest environments, lessons conducted along the shores of watersheds help activate biological processes, enhance overall performance, slow the onset of fatigue, and provide various additional benefits. These lessons also serve as a relatively independent means of healing and strengthening the developing bodies of adolescents, while significantly contributing to the formation of their volitional qualities. Importantly, in the context of volitional development, a key direction is the systematic and integrated application of such natural activities in conjunction with physical exercises. Hygienic rules and norms can also be utilized as tools of physical education for fostering volitional qualities in two distinct ways.

First, they act as an independent tool. For students, adhering to a daily routine—such as maintaining consistent sleeping, reading, and eating habits—is not always easy and demands a degree of willpower. The continuous motivation required to follow these routines significantly contributes to the development of volitional traits.

Second, hygiene norms function as supportive conditions, helping to promote health and amplify the effects of physical exercises ^[7].

Therefore, the main means of physical education contributing to the formation of volitional qualities in students include:

- Physical exercises,
- The healing forces of nature,
- Hygiene rules and norms.

These elements are closely interconnected, mutually reinforcing, and collectively determine the effectiveness of physical education. During adolescence, the nature of educational activities and peer dynamics changes considerably. Learning—like other activities—becomes more complex, requiring greater effort, autonomy, and responsibility. Adults also begin to expect more mature behavior from adolescents, including the consistent expression of volitional and personal characteristics. This is a natural process, as teenagers become intellectually sharper, physically stronger, and more socially aware. Their position among peers and public opinion about them begins to hold considerable significance.

In such situations, adolescents often face conflicting expectations from adults and peers, prompting them to make decisions that require considerable willpower ^[8]. These circumstances directly influence the manifestation and development of volitional traits. Based on a review and analysis of various studies on the development of volitional qualities in students, the author arrives at the following key conclusions: the development of volitional qualities in students is closely associated with moral education, as it involves the shaping of motives.

Willpower in students is expressed through a unity of opposing characteristics: courage and fear, desire and limitation, tenacity and weakness, endurance and impulsiveness. Students tend to prioritize volitional qualities above other personal traits. They often regard strong-willed individuals as role models and aspire to emulate them ^[9]. However, many researchers argue that the level of volitional development in students does not meet the expectations of today’s evolving social environment. Adolescents often lack proper organization, easily yield to challenges, are highly susceptible to peer influence, and may act in contradiction to previously

internalized norms and behaviors. Nonetheless, this does not imply regression or a decline in willpower when compared to younger students. Rather, the increased complexity of their social environment requires more advanced forms of self-regulation and the more active expression of volitional traits. During this stage, students begin to develop the ability to analyze their own behavior, assess their personal attitudes toward their surroundings, select role models, and impose self-demands. Crucially, their aspirations often exceed their current capabilities, leading to feelings of inadequacy or dissatisfaction. As a result, adolescents may view themselves as lacking willpower, which can negatively affect self-esteem.

In conclusion, adolescence is a unique period of human development. It is marked not only by intellectual curiosity, high energy, and a drive for activity, but also by the active evolution of personal characteristics, especially volitional traits. Thus, it is essential to identify and stimulate factors during this stage that encourage adolescents to continuously exercise their willpower, support its development, and integrate it as a core element of their personality.

Therefore, the means of physical education hold a special place among them ^[10]. An analysis of the composition of the means of physical education and their interrelation with the peculiarities of the development and manifestation of volitional qualities in students allowed us to determine their following potential. Physical education tools enable students to satisfy their desire for physical improvement, accelerate their development, strengthen their health, and meet their need for harmonious growth. They instill in students the desire to be role models, as well as to become individuals who have achieved notable success in sports, are physically fit, possess high personal qualities, and enjoy prestige. These tools nurture a natural desire in students to win in competition, to stand out from others, assert themselves, gain recognition, be first, increase their self-worth, take a respected place among peers, and be acknowledged and respected. They help develop a wide range of movement skills and abilities, allow students to test themselves in overcoming challenges, and nurture disciplined behavior. They fulfill teenagers' needs for dynamic movement, novelty, emotional variety, and communication with peers. They help form sustained motivation by instilling in students the need to attend physical education classes even when they are not intrinsically interested in the curriculum requirements. It was noted that the identified potentials of physical education tools in developing students' volitional qualities affect them to varying degrees. These potentials are not realized in isolation, but through an integrated pedagogical process—such as physical education classes, school sports activities, competitions, training in sports clubs, and similar settings. An analysis of the work done and its results led to the following general conclusions.

CONCLUSION

Equipping schools with sports facilities and equipment is not the most critical factor in forming volitional qualities. While such resources are very important for optimizing physical development, they are less decisive in the formation of strong willpower in students. A student may be strong and agile but still lack courage, initiative, or the ability to make independent decisions. Our observations of the volitional qualities' formation program indicate that exercises must be sufficiently challenging to foster volitional development. At the same time, tasks must be tailored to each student individually; otherwise, students may lose interest if they perceive the exercises as too difficult to master. This is supported by the general findings of the aforementioned study. Thus, planned and systematic efforts to utilize physical education for the development of volitional qualities in students have yielded positive outcomes. This purposeful approach is reflected in a marked increase in the number of students demonstrating a high level of initiative.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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